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Forecasting the generations of the Mediterranean fruit fly, *Ceratitis capitata* (Diptera: Tephritidae), using degree-day models on Valencia orange orchards throughout two fruiting seasons

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Abstract

This investigation includes degree-days (DD) and thermal developmental thresholds (T_0) as constant parameters for estimating the immature and mature stages of the generations of *Ceratitis capitata* (Weidenmann) (Diptera: Tephritidae). The thresholds of the immature stages (embryonic development, larval duration, and pupal duration) were recorded as 8.97, 4.2, and 8.61, respectively. The threshold temperature (T_0) for the mature stages (pre-oviposition period and duration of generation) was recorded as 6.43 and 7.05, respectively. The temperature ranges from 20 to 30°C was the optimum effective zone for the developmental rate of *C. capitata* stages. Fly activity data collected from pheromone traps, which were distributed throughout the field during two fruiting seasons, 2022 and 2023, were used to predict the peaks of adult emergence according to the DD model patterns. The accumulative heat units in degree-days during Valencia orange fruiting seasons ranged between (614.15 and 1856.5) in 2022 and (597.32 and 2379.86) in 2023, respectively. The data show four peaks each season in April, May, June, and July. These results are helpful in the IPM program pest control (Timing fly activity, choosing the insecticide type, and reducing the mean times of insecticide partial spray used).

Introduction

The genus *Citrus* (Swingle) family: Rutaceae is the most important fruit after bananas in the world, according to FAO Statista, 2023. In 2022, 10.6 million hectares of citrus were grown worldwide as recorded by FAO, yielding about 166.3 million tons of citrus (Garibay and Bernet, 2024). The economically important species of this genus are lemon, lime, sweet orange, sour orange, and

grapefruit. Citrus fruit is one of the most preferred flavors. It has a rich nutritive profile and is valued as nourishment. It is well known that citrus fruits and citrus products are a rich source of vitamins, minerals, fiber, and pectin that are essential for normal functions of the human body. Among all species, sweet orange is the major fruit crop of this genus and produces about 70% of total global citrus production (Hussain *et al.*,

2021). Valencia orange is the most important citrus crop in Egypt. According to global trade data (World Bank, 2024), Egypt is the second-largest exporter of oranges in the world after Spain. Approximately 4.1 million tons, or 33% of the total horticultural area, are citrus. The main orange cultivation is found in El Nobariya, El Beheira, Ismailia, and El Sharqia regions, respectively (CAPMAS, 2024). The most harmful fruit pest is the Mediterranean fruit fly, *Ceratitis capitata* (Weidenmann) (Diptera: Tephritidae), which causes significant damage and reduces both the quantity and quality of fruit. It is a quarantine pest affecting exporting (Ali, 2016, and Khan and Naveed, 2017). The developmental rate of *C. capitata* and its wild spread, survival, reproduction, and population dynamics are affected by temperature, which is the main directly critical environmental factor. Temperature affects their biological and ecological life and is important for good forecasting studies of insect populations (Dahi, 2003). In many insect species, the increment of temperature is fastening the rate of insect development, so the relationship between temperature and rate of development plays an important role in this study to estimate the temperature summations (Heat unit) required to complete a stage or entire life cycle.

This work aimed to study the relation between temperature and the developmental rate of the medfly, *C. capitata*, using thermal summation to detect the time of *C. capitata* pest management. The prediction of development and emergence is recognized as a step for pest control. Monitoring, using pheromone traps, and degree-day accumulation are valuable tools to predict pest population occurrence.

Materials and methods

1. Insect rearing:

Insects used in this study were established from a laboratory culture reared in the Horticultural Insects

Research Department-Plant Protection Research Institute-Agricultural Research Center, Giza, Egypt, at $25 \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$ and $70\% \pm 5\%$ RH. The artificial diet for larvae (Consisting of 330 gm of wheat bran, 85 gm of sugar, 85 gm of dried yeast, 5 gm of sodium benzoate, 5 gm of citric acid, and 500 ml of water) at a rate of 1ml egg/kg medium was used. Flies were reared in the laboratory for five successive generations. Adults were fed a diet consisting of protein hydrolysate and sugar at 1:10 gm (Manoukas, 2004).

2. Estimation of thermal requirements for *Ceratitis capitata* development:

One hundred newly laid eggs (1 hr. old) were collected and arranged in rows on small squares of black filter paper (1 cm^2) moistened with distilled water. All eggs were inspected under a stereoscope to ensure that the black card carried sound and healthy eggs. The black cards containing eggs were then inserted into Valencia orange fruits having holes measuring $1.5 \times 1.5\text{ cm}$ for each using sterilized forceps and sealed thoroughly with adhesive tape. Fifteen infested fruits were used for each temperature regime. The infested fruits were transferred into incubators at 20, 25, and 30°C . The infested fruits were checked twice daily throughout the experiment to record as accurately as possible the periods required for eclosion, larval development, and pupation. Emerged flies were sexed, and the mean values of the pre-oviposition period and generation time were calculated. The regression relationship between developmental rates, y (estimated as the inverse of duration, D (number of days required for development at that temperature, $1/D$), and temperature x was adopted based on the assumption that the temperature developmental rate relationship is linear above the lower threshold for development (Fletcher, 1989). The lower temperature threshold for development (T_0) was estimated by dividing the intercept by the slope of the linear regression, $T_0 = -a/b$ (Arnold, 1960). A constant number of thermal units (usually

expressed as day-degrees) above this threshold is required to complete development (Fletcher, 1989). The thermal constant K, the number of heat units required for 50% of individuals in a life stage to complete development, was derived for each temperature as $K = D(T - T_0)$, where T is the temperature at which development is completed (Arnold, 1960).

3. Seasonal fluctuation of *Ceratitis capitata* population in orange orchards:

The seasonal abundance of *C. capitata* was estimated by using white Jackson traps (Harris *et al.*, 1971) that were distributed in an area of about 5 feddans, which were cultivated with Valencia orange (*Citrus sinensis*) at El-Beheira Governorate. Three Jackson traps were powered with the sex attractant of trimedlure. The traps were hung on the shaded side of the fruiting trees at about two meters height. Each trap was 200 meters apart. The traps were weekly inspected for 15 successive weeks from the first week of April till the last week of July during the two fruiting periods of the 2022 and 2023 seasons. The captured males on each sticky cardboard inside each trap were counted. The number of captured Flies per Trap per Week (F/T/W) was used as a measure of fly abundance. The sex attractant wick of MFF, as well as sticky cardboard strips, were renewed every two weeks. Based on our estimations of T_0 for *C. capitata*, the daily maximum (T_{max}) and minimum (T_{min}) temperatures (Obtained from the Meteorological Station), the equations proposed by Richmond *et al.* (1983) were applied daily to estimate the number of heat units (H) acquired by an individual insect under field conditions on that day, as follows:

$H = \sum H_j$, where H = the number of thermal units required to complete development

$H_j = (T_{max.} + T_{min.}) / 2 - T_0$, if $T_{max.} > T_0$ and $T_{min.} > T_0$

$H_j = (T_{max.} - T_0)^2 / 2 (T_{max.} - T_{min.})$, if $T_{max.} > T_0$ and $T_{min.} < T_0$

$H_j = 0$, if $T_{max.} < T_0$ and $T_{min.} < T_0$

Data obtained were statistically analyzed according to ANOVA tests to determine the significance between treatments using SPSS software as described by Snedecor and Cochran (1967).

Results and discussion

Effect of thermal units and degree-days on certain biological aspects of *Ceratitis capitata*:

1. Thermal units needed to complete certain durations of immature and mature stages under laboratory conditions:

Temperature is an important environmental abiotic factor that affects the rate of development in all insect stages. This study observed a positive relationship between temperature and developmental rates of *C. capitata* from egg to adult stages. The thermal units are expressed as degree-days required for completing the development of each insect stage. Data presented in Tables (1 and 2) and Figure (1) show a lower developmental threshold temperature (T_0) for each developmental stage of *C. capitata*. The threshold temperatures of immature stages of *C. capitata* (Incubation period as well as larval and pupal durations) were 8.97, 4.20, and 8.61°C, respectively (Table 1). The threshold temperature (T_0) for the pre-oviposition period (Table 2) recorded 6.43, whereas the threshold temperature (T_0) for the duration of generation was 7.05°C. The temperature ranges from 20 to 30°C was the ideal effective zone for *C. capitata* stages. The rate of development increased with the increment of temperature in all mature as well as immature stages. All deposited eggs of *C. capitata* failed to hatch at 35°C. However, a significant decrease was obtained statistically in the case of the incubation period, larval and pupal durations, as well as the pre-oviposition period and the duration of generation with the increment of temperature.

Table (1): Developmental rates of *Ceratitits capitata* immature stages in Valencia orange at different constant temperatures.

Temp. (°C)	Egg stage			Larval stage			Pupal stage		
	Incubation period (day)	Rate of development	Thermal units	larval duration (day)	Rate of Development	Thermal units	Pupal duration (day)	Rate of development	Thermal units
20	3.70a	27.03	40.81	10.82a	9.24	170.96	13.74a	7.28	156.50
25	2.30b	43.48	36.87	8.42b	11.88	175.14	9.64b	10.37	158
30	1.90b	52.63	39.96	6.65c	15.04	171.57	7.33c	13.64	156.80
T ₀	-	-	8.97	-	-	4.20	-	-	8.61
F value	47.29	-	-	94.45	-	-	91.10	-	-
P value	0.000 *	-	-	0.000*	-	-	0.000*	-	-
LSD	0.48	-	-	0.74	-	-	1.18	-	-

Table (2): Developmental rates of *Ceratitits capitata* preoviposition period and duration of generation in Valencia orange at different constant temperatures.

Temp. (°C)	Preoviposition period			Generation		
	Preoviposition period (day)	Rate of development	Thermal units	Duration of generation (day)	Rate of development	Thermal units
20	6.70 a	14.93	90.92	34.96 a	2.86	452.73
25	4.50 b	22.22	83.57	24.86 b	4.02	446.24
30	3.80 c	26.32	89.57	19.68 b	5.08	451.66
T ₀	-	-	6.43	-	-	7.05
F value	60.62	-	-	24.43	-	-
P value	0.000 *	-	-	0.002 *	-	-
LSD	0.67	-	-	5.44	-	-

Figure (1): Linear correlation of developmental stages, preoviposition, and generation periods with degree-day units.

2. Relation between degree days and peaks of *Ceratitis capitata* adults in the field:

The results revealed four abundance peaks during the fruiting season of Valencia orange. As illustrated in Tables (3 and 4) and Figure (2), the obtained results indicated that the peaks of the *C. capitata* population in the season of 2023 were slightly higher than those recorded during the season of 2022. The peak values during the season of 2022 recorded 19.67, 23.67, 28, and 52.33 at

thermal units of 614.15, 925.73, 1226.50, and 1856.50, whereas the peak values of the 2023 season recorded 36, 62.33, 65.33, and 18.67 at thermal units of 597.32, 1065.27, 1411.96, and 2379.86, respectively. The cumulative daily degrees across generations ranged from 300.74 to 630 during the 2022 season and from 346.69 to 967.90 during the 2023 season. The cumulative daily degrees across generations ranged from 300.74 to 630 during the 2022 season and from 346.69 to 967.90 during the 2023 season.

Table (3): Comparative of the recorded peaks for *Ceratitis capitata* males in relation to the accumulative heat units in degree-days during Valencia orange fruiting seasons (2022 and 2023).

Series of peaks	Peaks of captured flies			DD's		Differences of DD, s between peaks		Mean of DD, s peaks
	2022	2023	Mean±SE	2022	2023	2022	2023	
1 st	19.67	36	27.84±5.77	614.15	597.32	614.15	597.32	605.74
2 nd	23.67	62.33	43±13.67	925.73	1065.27	311.58	467.95	389.76
3 rd	28	65.33	46.67±13.2	1226.5	1411.96	300.74	346.69	323.72
4 th	52.33	18.67	35.5±11.90	1856.5	2379.86	630	967.90	798.94
Mean±S.E.	30.92±3.67	45.58±5.57	38.25±2.09	1155.7	1363.59	464.12	594.96	529.54

Table (4): Monthly population density of *Ceratitis capitata* trapped males and accumulative heat units in degree-days (DD's) during two seasons.

Month	Average of male flies/trap/week			Average accumulative heat units in daily degrees		
	2022	2023	Mean±SE	2022	2023	Mean
April	11.25	24.5	17.87±4.68	388.10	378.11	383.10
May	23.93	51.73	37.83±9.83	1075.3	1073.71	1074.50
June	41.92	27.09	34.50±5.24	1780	1812.83	1796.44
July	26	13.44	19.72±4.44	2317.2	2371.50	2344.35

Figure (2): The relation between thermal heat units and population density of *Ceratitis capitata* using Jackson traps during the 2022 and 2023 fruiting seasons.

The range of temperature used to measure developmental rates in the laboratory (20-35°C) encompassed most of the minimum and maximum temperatures recorded in the field over the two study seasons. No immature stages of *C. capitata* developed at 35°C. Developmental times of *C. capitata* were shorter at 35°C than at 30°C, as previously reported by Duyck and Quilici (2002), which confirmed the obtained data, which could implicate 35°C as the upper thermal threshold for *C. capitata*, given that immature survival was relatively reduced at 30°C. Also, Ricalde *et al.* (2012) stated that survival during development was affected by 15 to 30°C, and significantly differed from survival at 20 to 25°C. At 35°C, immature stages did not develop.

The obtained results showed that the time for completing development of *C. capitata* stages ranged from 19.68 to 34.96 days at 20, 25, and 30°C. These results are in general agreement with data from previous studies on *C. capitata*, such as Duyck and Quilici (2002), who reported that durations of the immature stages ranged from 14.5 to 63.8 days at 30–15°C. Ricalde *et al.* (2012) studied the biological characteristics of *C. capitata* populations from Pelotas-RS (Temperate climate), Petrolina-PE (Tropical), and Campinas-SP (Subtropical) in Brazil and found that egg to adult developmental time for all three populations was inversely proportional to temperature; from 15 to 30°C, developmental time varied from 71.2 to 17.1, 70.2 to 17.1, and 68.5 to 16.9 days, respectively. Also, Bayoumy *et al.* (2021) reported that complete development of *C. capitata* ranged from 14 to 37 days at 20, 25, and 30°C.

Also, the results showed that the thermal units for the generation of *C. capitata* ranged from 446.24 to 452.73 DD. So, the present data of the DDs

required to complete development were higher than that estimated by Duyck and Quilici (2002), who reported that the thermal constant for total development of the immature stages of *C. capitata* was 260 DD. But the degree-day requirement was similar for all immature stages, except for the egg stage (Ricalde *et al.*, 2012). Immature development of *C. capitata* was estimated to require 373 and 424 DD for a complete generation (Bayoumy *et al.*, 2021).

The determination coefficients of the linear regression of developmental rates on temperature for *C. capitata* were close to one, indicating strong linearity of the model between 20 and 30°C and justifying the use of the temperature-summation model to estimate developmental rates over the tested range of temperatures. The linearity of this relationship was consistent with the findings of studies on other species of Tephritidae (Duyck and Quilici, 2002). This is important because the ability of DD models to accurately predict insect development patterns ranges from very good to poor, depending on the insect and the model used (Lischke *et al.*, 1997). Our results are close to those recorded by Faten *et al.* (2025). They studied the effect of threshold temperature on immature stages (Embryonic development, larval duration, pupal duration, pre-oviposition period, and duration). The results recorded 7.44, 5.01, 3.18°C, 7.08, and 8.96 for the immature and mature stages of *C. capitata*, respectively. The temperature from 20 to 30°C was the optimum effective zone for *C. capitata* stages.

In the field, males of *C. capitata* showed four peaks of abundance during Valencia orange fruiting periods (2022 and 2023). These data are confirmed with those obtained by Bjeliš and Pelicarić (2002), Martinez-Ferrer and Campos (2006), Afia (2007), and

Ghanim and Moustafa (2009), who recorded four to five peaks in Croatia (The first author), two distinct peaks of *C. capitata* activity in Spain (the second), but, in Egypt, both the third and fourth authors recorded three to four peaks of *C. capitata* in Qalubiya and Giza governorates (The third), and the latest found three annual peaks of seasonal activity for *C. capitata* in the Mansoura region. Environmental conditions, temporal patterns of host fruit availability, and crop sanitation practices are the main factors that can contribute to annual variations in *C. capitata* populations (Villiers *et al.*, 2013). Our results agree with those obtained by Faten *et al.* (2025). They discuss the results of laboratory experiments that were used in a DD model for *C. capitata* stages and correlated them with field fly activity data collected from pheromone traps during two fruiting seasons, 2022 and 2023, to predict the peaks of adult emergence according to the DD model patterns. We recorded four peaks each season in June, July, August, and September.

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